

An Onboard Transformer-Based Physics-Informed System for UAV Trajectory Prediction and State Classification in GNSS-denied Environments

Nicolas Souli, Yiannis Grigoriou, Panagiotis Chrysanthou, Panayiotis Kolios, and Georgios Ellinas

Abstract—This work introduces a real-time, lightweight system deployed onboard unmanned aerial vehicles (UAVs) that achieves the two-fold objective of state classification and trajectory prediction by integrating a Transformer-based physics-informed learning model with an extended Kalman filter (EKF). The proposed framework employs a two-stage sensor fusion mechanism that combines a physics-informed Transformer with an EKF-based measurement augmentation. In the first stage, an EKF fuses onboard sensor readings together with vision-derived measurements (optical flow measurements) and external sensor information (such as weather station data of wind speed and direction) to construct an augmented and denoised input measurement vector. In the second stage, the resulting filtered state estimates are fed into a physics-informed Transformer network that exploits shared feature learning to jointly enhance robustness and improve state classification and trajectory forecasting performance in Global Navigation Satellite System (GNSS)-denied environments. The proposed EKF-assisted AI framework is trained and validated on a custom dataset of UAV trajectories collected across various outdoor environments, and its prototype implementation is thoroughly assessed and validated in real-world outdoor experiments.

I. INTRODUCTION

With the rapid advancements in UAV technology, UAVs are increasingly used in a large number of civilian applications, where accurate UAV position estimation is becoming essential for autonomous flight to ensure safety while meeting latency, security, and reliability constraints. Typically, UAV localization is achieved using onboard sensors and GNSS, which serves as the primary positioning solution due to its meter-level accuracy under open-sky and favorable environmental conditions [1]. Nevertheless, accurate position and state estimation for reliable and robust navigation [2], [3] remains a critical challenge when GNSS signals are degraded, obstructed, or inaccessible, leading to the need for robust and efficient navigation solutions, particularly in GNSS-denied environments or in scenarios where onboard sensors may malfunction [4], [5].

Recent research has primarily considered single-task neural network (NN) approaches for UAV state classification or trajectory prediction, frequently based on recurrent architectures such as recurrent neural networks (RNNs) and

long short-term memory (LSTM) [6], [7]. However, as these models demonstrate limited capability in modeling long-range temporal relationships over extended time horizons, Transformer-based techniques leveraging self-attention have gained increasing attention and have shown improved effectiveness in learning long-term temporal structure in time-series data [8], [9]. Furthermore, reservoir computing (RC) approaches have been investigated as lightweight alternatives for temporal modeling, offering computational efficiency and fast training while maintaining accurate prediction performance [10]. In addition, Transformer-based architectures combined with RC demonstrated a balance between trajectory prediction accuracy and onboard feasibility for UAV applications [11]. Further, physics-informed Transformers incorporate domain constraints to improve forecasting and classification accuracy beyond data-driven methods [12], [13]. However, their effectiveness for GNSS-denied autonomous UAV navigation remains largely unexplored.

This work extends our previously proposed Transformer-based multi-task learning framework (MTLF-FVO) [14], which provided robust UAV localization and state identification following a data-driven, Transformer-based multi-task architecture that combined onboard telemetry [e.g., Inertial measurement unit (IMU), velocity, acceleration, and external sensor modalities such as wind speed and direction] with vision-derived feature-based visual odometry measurements. Specifically, this work presents a lightweight, onboard, real-time UAV system for joint state identification and trajectory prediction [Enhanced Multi-task Transformer-based Physics-informed (EMT-TPI)], by incorporating a physics-informed Transformer with a two-stage sensor-fusion pipeline. In the first stage, an EKF fuses multi-modal onboard inertial measurements with vision-derived measurements (e.g., optical flow) to generate an augmented, uncertainty-aware state estimate, while in the second stage a physics-informed Transformer leverages these filtered estimates to estimate the UAV trajectory and classify the flight state. By fusing EKF (recursive uncertainty propagation) with physics-based regularization, EMT-TPI mitigates the limitations of model-driven filtering, data-driven forecasting, and standalone physics-informed learning, making it suitable for real-time operational deployment.

The main contributions of this work are summarized as follows: (i) the design of a Transformer-based multi-task learning (MTL) architecture that jointly performs UAV state identification and 3D trajectory prediction in GNSS-denied environments using EKF-augmented multi-modal inertial, external sensor measurements, and vision inputs for safety monitoring and risk-aware autonomy; (ii) the use of an EKF-assisted physics-informed training objective that improves

N. Souli, Y. Grigoriou, P. Chrysanthou and G. Ellinas are with the Department of Electrical and Computer Engineering and the KIOS Research and Innovation Center of Excellence (KIOS CoE), University of Cyprus, Nicosia, Cyprus. P. Kolios is with the Department of Computer Science and the KIOS CoE, University of Cyprus. Emails: {nsouli02, grigoriou.yiannis, chrysanthou.a.panagiotis, pkolios, gellinas}@ucy.ac.cy
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forecasting accuracy and robustness; (iii) a lightweight onboard prototype implementation enabling real-time sensor data handling and low-latency inference on resource-constrained UAV platforms; and (iv) extensive testing of the prototype under practical operating conditions, demonstrating reliable state classification and accurate 3D trajectory forecasting.

II. RELATED WORK

Conventional UAV state estimation techniques are mainly based on simultaneous localization and mapping (SLAM) [15] and visual-inertial odometry (VIO) [16] for continuous pose tracking. However, their increased computational cost and performance degradation in challenging outdoor environments have led to the investigation of learning-based approaches [17], which have demonstrated improved performance across diverse conditions.

Model-based UAV trajectory prediction is typically formulated using nonlinear rigid-body state-space dynamics with recursive Bayesian estimation, where EKF is widely utilized due to its computational efficiency and real-time suitability for onboard use. In [18], the authors presented a quadrotor translational and rotational dynamics method within an EKF for recursive state propagation, while in a similar vein, in [19] a quaternion-based EKF formulation was proposed to improve attitude-estimation stability. Moreover, [20] proposed an inertial propagation with visual updates in a tightly coupled visual-inertial filtering framework for micro aerial vehicle state estimation. In addition, visual-inertial systems were investigated to enhance trajectory prediction and robustness through IMU integration, or keyframe-based optimization [21], [22].

In parallel, UAV trajectory prediction has also been addressed using data-driven learning models, with Transformer-based architectures being used to model longer temporal dependencies (as compared to RNNs/LSTMs) [8]. However, existing Transformer-based models may still degrade across diverse scenarios and extended horizons [23], motivating more robust hybrid forecasting strategies. Thus, physics-informed Transformer models have been recently investigated for long-horizon prediction. For example, [24] introduced a physics-informed Transformer network for hypersonic glide vehicle trajectory forecasting; however, its dependence on synthetic trajectories, fixed-length input sequences, limited physical modeling, and the absence of real-world outdoor evaluation restricts its generalization to more complex scenarios. Also, [25] proposed a physics-informed deep learning approach for highway vehicle prediction, but its one-dimensional formulation, fixed-length inputs, and reliance on synthetic data limit applicability to multi-dimensional and dynamically rich environments.

Further, [26] proposed a neural network model to solve multiple objectives by sharing representations, which has been demonstrated to improve generalization and reduce overfitting [27]. Typical MTL methods employ parameter sharing and task-specific modules (e.g., attention mechanism) [27]. In UAV scenarios, MTL can jointly optimize objectives such as state identification and trajectory prediction by exploiting shared features, thereby reducing dependence

on large annotated datasets that are often difficult to acquire [28].

Although Transformer-based methods have demonstrated increased performance in single-task trajectory forecasting or classification, their integration into a unified, physics-informed MTL framework for UAV operations remains limited, particularly under real-world conditions where sensing is multi-modal and uncertainty must be managed online. Moreover, existing studies are often evaluated on synthetic data and frequently assume fixed-length input sequences, which constrains deployment in practical flight scenarios. To overcome these limitations, this work proposes EMT-TPI, a lightweight onboard architecture that combines two-stage multi-modal sensor fusion, where initially an EKF fuses onboard inertial measurements with vision-based measurements and external sensing to create an augmented measurement vector, and subsequently a physics-informed Transformer-based MTL model jointly performs real-time UAV state identification and 3D trajectory prediction in GNSS-denied outdoor environments.

III. SYSTEM ARCHITECTURE

The proposed system employs a modular, payload software development kit (PSDK)-based architecture to process UAV telemetry, onboard camera streams, and external weather-sensor measurements in real time. As shown in Fig. 1, raw telemetry data is acquired directly through the UAV’s (DJI) PSDK. The system subscribes to telemetry data topics and processes the camera video feed to compute visual odometry (VO) measurements. Both the frame-based visual odometry and the telemetry data streams are fused through a 12-state EKF to estimate UAV position, velocity, attitude, and accelerometer biases. The fused state estimates, together with weather-related inputs, are then forwarded to the multitask Transformer model for trajectory prediction and state identification.

Fig. 1: EMT-TPI model framework.

A. Feature-based Visual Odometry

This section describes the feature-based visual odometry module used to estimate the UAV’s horizontal displacement from consecutive camera frames [14].

1) *Feature-based Motion Estimation for UAV Navigation:* This module runs in real time on the onboard compute stack using DJI's PSDK at 10 Hz. For each incoming frame, the pipeline applies a region-of-interest mask, extracts and matches sparse features to the previous frame, rejects outliers through RANSAC [29], and estimates the inter-frame pixel displacement. The displacement is then converted to metric units using the camera field of view (FOV) and the measured altitude, rotated to compensate for the UAV heading, and integrated over time. Since VO alone accumulates drift and becomes unreliable during strong vertical motion or non-downward viewing, the implementation fuses the visual displacement with onboard telemetry velocities.

2) *Image Processing:* Each frame is pre-processed to improve robustness and reduce the computational cost of feature extraction. The implementation crops the input to a centered square region and applies a circular binary mask. This masking suppresses peripheral regions that often exhibit higher distortion and motion blur, while retaining the central region that provides more stable feature tracks. The masked image is then converted to grayscale before feature extraction.

3) *Sparse Feature Extraction and Matching:* Sparse keypoints and binary descriptors are extracted using ORB (Oriented FAST and Rotated BRIEF), a lightweight feature extractor/descriptor that is well-suited for real-time operation. The descriptors are matched between consecutive frames using a brute-force matcher with Hamming distance and cross-check enabled [30], which yields mutually consistent correspondences. Let $\{(\mathbf{p}_{pixel_i}^{k-1}, \mathbf{p}_{pixel_i}^k)\}_{i=1}^M$ denote the initial set of matched keypoints in the previous and current frames, respectively, with M the total number of matched keypoints between the two consecutive frames.

4) *Outlier Rejection and Pixel Displacement Estimation:* To reject false correspondences caused by repetitive textures or fast viewpoint changes, the implementation estimates a ground-plane homography using RANSAC and retains only the geometrically consistent matches (with a 5-pixel reprojection threshold) [29]. The homography is used to identify geometrically consistent correspondences (inliers) and is not decomposed to recover pose. Given N inlier matches, the average pixel displacement (for the x and y directions) is computed as $\Delta x = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N (x_{pixel_i}^k - x_{pixel_i}^{k-1})$ and $\Delta y = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N (y_{pixel_i}^k - y_{pixel_i}^{k-1})$.

5) *Pixel-to-World Coordinate Transformation:* The average pixel displacement $(\Delta x, \Delta y)$ is converted to metric displacement under the ground-plane approximation. With alt denoting the UAV's altitude, the physical footprint of the image is computed as $FOV_x = 2 \cdot alt \cdot \tan(\frac{\theta_h}{2})$ and $FOV_y = 2 \cdot alt \cdot \tan(\frac{\theta_v}{2})$ (all angular quantities, including the horizontal and vertical FOVs θ_h and θ_v are expressed in radians).

Also, the meters-per-pixel factors in horizontal (m_x) and vertical directions (m_y) are determined as $m_x = \frac{FOV_x}{W}$ and $m_y = \frac{FOV_y}{H}$ with H and W denoting the frame's height and width, respectively. Therefore, the translation from pixel to meter units $\Delta x_{real}, \Delta y_{real}$ is calculated as $\Delta x_{real} = \Delta x \cdot m_x$ and $\Delta y_{real} = \Delta y \cdot m_y$.

6) *Compensation for Drone Orientation:* The computed displacement vector (in meters) is aligned with the navigation reference frame by compensating for the UAV heading angle ψ [29]. A standard two-dimensional rotation is applied to obtain $\Delta x', \Delta y'$

$$\begin{bmatrix} \Delta x' \\ \Delta y' \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \cos \psi & -\sin \psi \\ \sin \psi & \cos \psi \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \Delta x_{real} \\ \Delta y_{real} \end{bmatrix}. \quad (1)$$

7) *Visual-Telemetry Fusion and Gating:* To improve robustness in GNSS-denied operation, the implementation fuses the VO displacement with the horizontal velocity components provided by onboard telemetry.

B. EKF Module

An EKF is used to fuse high-rate IMU measurements with measurements of position, velocity, and heading. The EKF estimates a 12-dimensional state that includes the full 3D kinematics, Euler attitude (Euler angle vector), and accelerometer bias.

C. State Vector

The state vector $\mathcal{X}_k \in \mathbb{R}^{12}$ at time step k is defined as $\mathcal{X}_k = [p_k^T \ v_k^T \ \Theta_k^T \ b_{a,k}^T]^T$, where $p_k = [p_x, p_y, p_z]^T$ denotes the estimated position (in meters), updated using fused VO/telemetry measurements, while $v_k = [v_x, v_y, v_z]^T$ denotes the velocity (m/s). The vehicle orientation (Euler attitude) is given by $\Theta_k = [\phi, \theta, \psi]^T$, represented by Euler angles (roll, pitch, yaw) in radians. Additionally, accelerometer errors are modeled by $b_{a,k} = [b_{ax}, b_{ay}, b_{az}]^T$ for the accelerometer bias (m/s²).

D. Process Model (Prediction Step)

The prediction step is performed by propagating the state forward using IMU measurements as control inputs. Let $u_k = [\tilde{a}_k^T, \tilde{\omega}_k^T]^T$ be the raw IMU (accelerometer, angular velocity) measurements. In the implemented model, only the accelerometer measurements are corrected by subtracting the estimated accelerometer bias as $\hat{a}_k = \tilde{a}_k - b_{a,k}$, while the angular velocity measurements are defined as $\hat{\omega}_k = \tilde{\omega}_k$.

1) *Attitude Update:* The rate of change of Euler angles is related to the body-frame angular velocity $\hat{\omega}_k = [\omega_{x,k}, \omega_{y,k}, \omega_{z,k}]^T$ by the transformation matrix $W(\Theta)$

$$\dot{\Theta} = W(\Theta)\hat{\omega} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & \sin \phi \tan \theta & \cos \phi \tan \theta \\ 0 & \cos \phi & -\sin \phi \\ 0 & \sin \phi / \cos \theta & \cos \phi / \cos \theta \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \omega_x \\ \omega_y \\ \omega_z \end{bmatrix}. \quad (2)$$

The discrete update is then computed as $\Theta_{k+1} = \Theta_k + \dot{\Theta}_k \Delta k$.

2) *Velocity and Position Update:* The accelerometer measurements specific force on the body frame. This measurement is first rotated to the Earth frame using the rotation matrix $R(\Theta_k)$ and then used to compute $a_{earth} = R(\Theta_k)\hat{a}_k$. In the current implementation, the accelerometer input is treated as linear acceleration. The discrete kinematics (velocity and position) are defined as $v_{k+1} = v_k + a_{earth}\Delta k$ and $p_{k+1} = p_k + v_k\Delta k + \frac{1}{2}a_{earth}\Delta k^2$, respectively.

3) *Bias Estimation*: Sensor biases are estimated recursively within the filter. In the prediction model, the accelerometer bias is treated as a random walk process driven by process noise, implying that it is assumed to be constant between time steps with small stochastic drift (i.e., $b_{a,k+1} = b_{a,k}$). The Jacobian matrix F couples accelerometer bias errors to the velocity states through $\partial v / \partial b_a \approx -R(\Theta_k)\Delta k$. Consequently, when a discrepancy arises between the predicted state (integrated from IMU data) and the measured observations (position or velocity), the Kalman gain K projects this measurement residual (innovation) onto the bias states, continuously correcting b_a to reduce overall estimation error.

E. Measurement Model (Update Step)

Three types of measurements are processed by the EKF, each sampled at 10Hz.

1) *Position Update*: A 3D position measurement $z_{pos,k} \in \mathbb{R}^3$ is created by integrating the VO computed displacements in the local frame and combining them with the onboard rangefinder measurements that are incorporated as $z_{pos,k} = H_{pos} \mathcal{X}_k + \nu_{pos,k}$. The measurement matrix used to extract position states for the innovation computation is $H_{pos} = \begin{bmatrix} I_{3 \times 3} & 0_{3 \times 9} \end{bmatrix}$. An adaptive noise model is applied to position updates, when the horizontal innovation exceeds a threshold, the measurement covariance $R_{pos,k}$ increases to down-weight outlier measurements.

2) *Velocity Update*: Velocity measurements $z_{vel,k} \in \mathbb{R}^3$ are incorporated using the measurement matrix $H_{vel} = \begin{bmatrix} 0_{3 \times 3} & I_{3 \times 3} & 0_{3 \times 6} \end{bmatrix}$.

3) *Heading Update*: A magnetometer heading measurement $z_{head,k} = \psi_{mag,k}$ (converted to radians) is used to mitigate yaw drift through the measurement matrix $H_{head} = \begin{bmatrix} 0_{1 \times 8} & 1 & 0_{1 \times 3} \end{bmatrix}$. The yaw innovation is mapped to $(-\pi, \pi]$ to handle angle discontinuities.

F. EKF Algorithm

The recursive estimation process consists of two stages: prediction and update.

1) *Prediction Step*: First, the state estimate $\mathcal{X}_{k|k-1}$ and error covariance $P_{k|k-1}$ are computed using the process model $f(\cdot)$ and its Jacobian F_k as

$$\hat{\mathcal{X}}_{k|k-1} = f(\hat{\mathcal{X}}_{k-1|k-1}, u_k), \quad (3)$$

$$P_{k|k-1} = F_k P_{k-1|k-1} F_k^T + Q_k, \quad (4)$$

where Q_k is the process noise covariance matrix.

2) *Update Step*: Upon receiving the measurement vector z_k , the innovation \tilde{y}_k and its covariance S_k are calculated

$$\tilde{y}_k = z_k - h(\hat{\mathcal{X}}_{k|k-1}), \quad (5)$$

$$S_k = H_k P_{k|k-1} H_k^T + R_k, \quad (6)$$

where $h(\cdot)$ is the measurement function, H_k is the measurement Jacobian, and R_k is the measurement noise covariance. The Kalman gain K_k is then derived as $K_k = P_{k|k-1} H_k^T S_k^{-1}$. Finally, the posterior state estimate $\mathcal{X}_{k|k}$ and error covariance $P_{k|k}$ are updated

$$\hat{\mathcal{X}}_{k|k} = \hat{\mathcal{X}}_{k|k-1} + K_k \tilde{y}_k, \quad (7)$$

$$P_{k|k} = (I - K_k H_k) P_{k|k-1}. \quad (8)$$

G. Transformer-based Physics-informed Model

A sequence of Transformer encoder blocks, comprising layer normalization, multi-head self-attention, and feed-forward layers, is employed to model temporal correlations in the input sequences. The proposed neural network model follows a two-branch design, where the first branch computes continuous 3D trajectory forecasts, while the second branch performs discrete UAV state classification. Positional encoding is applied to preserve sequence ordering, and time-distributed fully connected layers are used to map the encoded features to the required outputs (trajectory prediction and state classification).

To enhance trajectory prediction performance by implementing physical motion constraints, a physics-informed loss module is introduced within the Transformer-based architecture. This loss component augments the standard trajectory mean-squared error (MSE) with additional physics-based and axis-dependent penalty terms, implemented through a weighted multi-component formulation with scaling coefficients. The resulting physics-informed objective comprises four main components, as summarized below.

Physics-informed trajectory loss: First, a weighted mean-squared error (wMSE) is computed over the predicted 3D positions, where the vertical component is emphasized to better capture altitude variations

$$\text{wMSE} = \frac{1}{NT} \sum_{i=1}^N \sum_{k=1}^T \left[(\tilde{p}_x)^2 + (\tilde{p}_y)^2 + 10(\tilde{p}_z)^2 \right], \quad (9)$$

where $\tilde{p}_x = (p_{x_{i,k}} - \hat{p}_{x_{i,k}})$, $\tilde{p}_y = (p_{y_{i,k}} - \hat{p}_{y_{i,k}})$, $\tilde{p}_z = (p_{z_{i,k}} - \hat{p}_{z_{i,k}})$, N denotes the batch size, T is the prediction horizon, and k the current sampling index (time-step) while $(p_{x_{i,k}}, p_{y_{i,k}}, p_{z_{i,k}})$ and $(\hat{p}_{x_{i,k}}, \hat{p}_{y_{i,k}}, \hat{p}_{z_{i,k}})$ are the ground-truth and predicted positions, respectively.

Next, kinematic quantities, such as velocity and acceleration, are computed from the predicted trajectory using finite differences with sampling interval Δk

$$\hat{\mathbf{v}}_{i,k} = \frac{\hat{\mathbf{p}}_{i,k} - \hat{\mathbf{p}}_{i,k-1}}{\Delta k}, \quad \hat{\mathbf{a}}_{i,k} = \frac{\hat{\mathbf{v}}_{i,k} - \hat{\mathbf{v}}_{i,k-1}}{\Delta k}, \quad (10)$$

where $\hat{\mathbf{p}}_{i,k} = [\hat{p}_{x_{i,k}}, \hat{p}_{y_{i,k}}, \hat{p}_{z_{i,k}}]^T$. A physics residual is then defined as the deviation of the predicted acceleration from gravity (assuming no thrust measurement is available), with $g = 9.81 \text{ m/s}^2$

$$\mathcal{R}_{\text{phys}} = \frac{1}{N(T-2)} \sum_{i=1}^N \sum_{k=3}^T \|\hat{\mathbf{a}}_{i,k} - [0, 0, -g]^T\|_2^2. \quad (11)$$

The gravity-consistency residual in Eq. (11) is applied only to flight segments in which thrust variations are minimal (e.g., *IDLE-HOVER* and low-acceleration motion). For maneuvering modes (e.g., *ASCEND*, *DESCEND*, and *TURN*), the residual is down-weighted by applying class-conditional weighting using ground-truth mode labels during training.

To further improve robustness to outliers and separately control vertical and horizontal accuracy, mean absolute error (MAE) penalty terms are introduced on the altitude (p_{z_k}) and the planar coordinates (p_{x_k} and p_{y_k})

$$Z_{\text{MAE}} = \frac{1}{NT} \sum_{i=1}^N \sum_{k=1}^T |\tilde{p}_z|, \quad (12)$$

$$XY_{\text{MAE}} = \frac{1}{NT} \sum_{i=1}^N \sum_{k=1}^T (|\tilde{p}_x| + |\tilde{p}_y|). \quad (13)$$

The final trajectory loss is the weighted sum of the aforementioned terms, where λ_{phys} , α_z , and β_{xy} are scalar coefficients used to balance physics residual and the MAE penalty terms

$$\mathcal{L}_{\text{traj}} = w\text{MSE} + \lambda_{\text{phys}} \mathcal{R}_{\text{phys}} + \alpha_z Z_{\text{MAE}} + \beta_{xy} XY_{\text{MAE}}. \quad (14)$$

Finally, the overall multi-task objective combines the trajectory loss with the binary cross-entropy loss [31] for state classification using equal weights

$$\mathcal{L} = 0.5 \mathcal{L}_{\text{traj}} + 0.5 \mathcal{L}_{\text{BCE}}. \quad (15)$$

The training procedure employs a neural network model checkpoint to save the weights achieving the minimum validation loss, and early stopping to terminate optimization when the validation loss fails to improve for a specified number of epochs. Flight telemetry obtained through the PSDK is logged to a database for offline labeling and subsequent analysis. Each time step is annotated into one of five flight modes [IDLE-HOVER, ASCEND, DESCEND, TURN, or HMSL (horizontal movement straight line)] using threshold rules for altitude deviation, yaw rate, and horizontal displacement. The labeled time series are then converted into overlapping input–output pairs using a sliding-window scheme. For example, the proposed EMT-TPI employs a sliding window of 120 samples (12 s at 0.1 s time intervals) and predicts the look-ahead horizon of 120 samples (12 s) for both 3D trajectory forecasting and the corresponding flight-mode sequence (state classification). It must be noted that for the proposed onboard system, a pre-trained EMT-TPI model is exported to ONNX for low-latency onboard inference [32].

IV. EMT-TPI ALGORITHM

Algorithm 1 summarizes the proposed EMT-TPI processing framework for UAV trajectory prediction and state classification using EKF-assisted, physics-informed learning in GNSS-denied conditions. Initially, multi-modal measurements (onboard inertial sensing and vision-derived data) are fused through an EKF to form an augmented, uncertainty-aware state estimate, which is then organized as an input sequence together with multi-class flight-mode labels. A sliding-window scheme, parameterized by the input size (IS), window size (WS), and prediction look-ahead size (HS), reshapes the training procedure’s samples that are subsequently split into training, validation, and test sets. The resulting sequences are used to train the multi-task Transformer model configured with selected hyperparameters and optimized using a physics-informed trajectory loss in conjunction with a classification loss. The proposed system’s performance is presented using the Euclidean distance error between predicted and ground-truth positions and standard class-wise metrics (Precision, Recall, and F1-score) for flight-mode classification [33].

Algorithm 1 EMT-TPI Training and Onboard Inference Framework

Model Input: Onboard, external, and visual-odometry measurements processed through EKF-based fusion

- 1: **procedure** (Model Initialization and Offline Training)
- 2: Configuration of EMT-TPI neural network model hyperparameters
- 3: Reshaping and normalization of data (input) sequences
- 4: Training and validation using the EKF-assisted physics-informed neural network model
- 5: Model extraction to ONNX format for real-time inference
- 6: **end procedure**
- 7: **procedure** (Online Data Acquisition and Inference)
- 8: Sensor measurement collection with the use of PSDK
- 9: Visual odometry computation using the camera stream
- 10: EKF sensor fusion
- 11: **if** Drone has landed **then**
- 12: UAV operation completed
- 13: **else**
- 14: Store data into the system’s database
- 15: Feed the collected data to the EMT-TPI model
- 16: EMT-TPI inference using the EKF-augmented input sequence
- 17: **end if**
- 18: **end procedure**

Model Output: Future UAV 3D trajectory and flight-state predictions

V. PERFORMANCE EVALUATION

A. Hardware Configuration

Data collection and experimental evaluation are conducted using the DJI Matrice 300 RTK or 350 RTK platforms, selected for their compatibility with onboard development and payload integration. Both UAVs are equipped with a DJI Zenmuse H20T camera to support vision-based measurements (e.g., for visual odometry) and an NVIDIA Jetson Xavier NX module to execute the proposed onboard software in real time, with an average measured end-to-end onboard latency (measured runtime) of 150 ms. Using DJI’s PSDK, the Jetson interfaces directly with the UAV telemetry and sensor streams, while an external TriSonica Mini wind and weather sensor provides wind speed and direction measurements for enhanced situational awareness. The overall hardware configuration is depicted in Fig. 2.

Fig. 2: EMT-TPI hardware onboard configuration: (a) UAV agent, (b) Embedded processing unit, (c) E-Port module.

B. Data Acquisition and Annotation

The dataset used in this work is publicly available on Zenodo and is collected using the proposed system prototype, referred to as Dataset-1 [34]. Dataset-1 encompasses 18 unique real-world drone 3D flights, amounting to roughly 15 minutes of flight time per mission and a total of 111,082 entries. The dataset is divided into 65% for training, 15% for validation, and 20% for testing purposes. Dataset-1 includes a broad set of drone sensor features, as can be seen in Fig. 3, but also incorporates outputs from the EKF, providing enhanced positional accuracy and additional estimation data. Also, the dataset includes annotations for the UAV operational modes, facilitating the classification procedure.

Figure 3 depicts the feature correlation matrix of the input features utilized by EMT-TPI, where warmer color variants demonstrate positive correlation and cooler variants describe negative correlation. As expected, strong correlations are observed among localization variables, particularly between the raw position components and their EKF-filtered counterparts (e.g., position_z with kalmanZ, and position_x/position_y with kalmanLat/kalmanLong), confirming consistency between measured and filtered state representations. A second correlated cluster appears in the attitude features, where d_roll and d_pitch exhibit high mutual correlation, while d_yaw shows a noticeable correlation with heading, reflecting the coupling between yaw dynamics and heading changes. In contrast, wind-related variables wind_speed and wind_angle exhibit weak correlation with most kinematic states, indicating that they provide complementary information rather than reproducing inertial/pose measurements. Overall, the correlation matrix presents a feature set that supports robust sensor fusion and improved generalization in GNSS-denied scenarios.

Fig. 3: Feature Correlation Matrix.

C. Experimental Results

This section presents the experimental evaluation of the EMT-TPI model. Its position prediction accuracy is assessed by comparing the predicted trajectory against ground truth (GT, obtained from GPS+RTK) data from Dataset-1. In addition, the ability of the model to correctly identify the state of the UAV is examined by comparing the UAV's predicted and actual states in a series of complex 3D flight experiments. It is important to note that to evaluate GNSS-denied performance, all GNSS measurements are excluded from EMT-TPI inputs during inference and GPS+RTK is

used only to provide ground-truth reference trajectories for evaluation purposes. Also, GPS+RTK geodetic coordinates (latitude, longitude, altitude) are mapped to a local East-North-Up (ENU) frame by converting latitude and longitude with the use of a Haversine-based approximation with respect to a reference origin, while altitude is used directly for the Up component (therefore all errors are evaluated in meters).

Specifically, a physics-informed Transformer network is implemented in Keras/TensorFlow to perform multi-step trajectory forecasting and flight-mode classification. The model operates at a sampling interval of $\Delta k = 0.1$ s and uses a fixed historical context window of $WS=120$ samples (12 s) to predict a future horizon of $HS=120$ steps (12 s). Input features consist of 22 telemetry features (wind speed/direction, battery voltage/current, attitude quaternion, linear and angular velocities, linear accelerations, ESC speed/voltage, commanded roll/pitch/yaw rates, and heading) augmented with Kalman filter outputs kalmanLat, kalmanLong, kalmanZ. To prevent leakage, the dataset is split by flight ID into 65% training and 15% validation sets, with sequences sorted by seq (sequence ID) or timestamp prior to window extraction. Also, it must be noted that the testing phase is conducted on experimental trials that were not included in the training and validation phase. The network consists of two parallel Transformer encoder branches (trajectory and classification), each formed by $N_{attn}=6$ stacked self-attention blocks with sinusoidal positional encoding. Each block uses multi-head self-attention with $n_h=6$ heads and key dimension $d_k=64$, followed by a feed-forward sublayer of width $d_{ff}=512$, residual connections, layer normalization, and a dropout rate of 0.1 is applied to the attention output. The trajectory branch produces 3D position predictions through a time-distributed linear layer, and the classification branch outputs estimates for the five flight states (IDLE-HOVER, ASCEND, TURN, HMSL, DESCEND) using a time-distributed sigmoid layer. Training uses the Adam optimizer (with learning rate 10^{-4}), batch size 64, and early stopping (with patience 15 epochs). The multi-task objective combines a physics-informed trajectory loss and binary cross-entropy classification loss with weights 0.5 and 0.5, respectively. For state classification, one logit per state is learned using sigmoid activations and binary cross-entropy on one-hot targets, while a single state is selected at each time step through argmax. The trajectory loss includes an axis-weighted MSE term, a physics residual regularizer with scalar coefficient $\lambda_{phys} = 0.03$, and additional MAE penalties on the vertical and lateral components with scalar weights $\alpha_z=20$ and $\beta_{xy}=12$.

The trajectory loss during 50 training epochs is illustrated in Fig. 4, where both training and validation loss converge within the first 10 epochs and stabilize near 1.0, demonstrating consistent generalization performance.

Table I describes the average Euclidean positional error (under a GNSS-denied input setting where only on-board inertial, vision, and external sensor measurements are utilized) over a 12 s forecast horizon ($WS=120$), comparing the proposed EMT-TPI against complementary learning- and filtering-based baseline techniques [data-driven (conventional) Transformer (e.g., MTLF-FVO), LSTM, and VO+EKF, using the same configuration parameters and resource constraints]. Compared to GNSS-dependent solutions, EMT-TPI performs GNSS-denied trajectory prediction (over

Fig. 4: EMT-TPI loss curve.

TABLE I: Average Euclidean distance error for trajectory prediction using WS=120 and HS=120.

Time (s)	EMT-TPI	EMT-TPI-NE	MTLF-FVO	MTLF-FVO-NE	LSTM	VO+EKF
t+1	5.96	7.33	7.94	10.65	17.91	15.57
t+2	5.71	6.95	7.80	10.44	17.24	-
t+3	5.89	6.93	7.66	10.53	16.59	-
t+4	5.97	6.88	7.62	10.31	16.05	-
t+5	6.16	6.80	7.77	10.14	15.71	-
t+6	6.13	6.93	7.90	10.18	15.56	-
t+7	6.10	7.09	7.86	10.15	15.61	-
t+8	6.37	7.13	7.97	10.16	15.86	-
t+9	6.64	7.18	8.15	10.30	16.23	-
t+10	6.91	7.36	8.37	10.50	16.85	-
t+11	7.33	7.55	8.74	10.64	19.09	-
t+12	7.90	8.12	9.02	10.98	21.01	-

long-horizon) by employing an EKF-assisted Transformer architecture, where the EKF fuses onboard inertial and vision measurements to produce an uncertainty-aware state estimate that is subsequently utilized by the proposed system for location estimation (with GPS+RTK used exclusively as ground truth only for evaluation purposes). Across all prediction steps, EMT-TPI achieves higher location estimation performance, ranging from 5.96 m at $t+1$ and 5.71 m at $t+2$ to 7.90 m at $t+12$. In comparison, MTLF-FVO exhibits consistently larger errors (e.g., 7.94 m at $t+1$ and 9.02 m at $t+12$), while the no-EKF (NE) variants further degrade performance (e.g., 10.65 m at $t+1$ and 10.98 m at $t+12$ for MTLF-FVO-NE). The LSTM baseline exhibits degraded performance across the horizon, increasing from 17.91 m at $t+1$ to 21.01 m at $t+12$. Finally, the VO+EKF baseline is presented only for the one-step prediction ($t+1$ as EKF is not a horizon forecaster), where it achieves 15.57 m error, highlighting that standalone recursive filtering is not sufficient for accurate long-horizon forecasting and motivating the proposed EKF-assisted Transformer integration for GNSS-denied UAV trajectory prediction.

Furthermore, Fig. 5 illustrates the cumulative distribution function (CDF) of the Euclidean distance error for the predicted trajectories. The results demonstrate that the proposed system (EMT-TPI) can achieve accurate location estimation in a GNSS-denied environment with a 50th percentile error of 6.875 m. Also, the error increases gradually at higher percentiles, reaching 11.81 m at the 80th percentile and 19.27 m at the 95th percentile, highlighting the worst-case deviations observed across the evaluation procedure.

Figure 6 illustrates mean absolute error (MAE) of EMT-TPI over a forecast horizon of 12 s, where the x-, y-, and z-axes represent the local ENU frame coordinates. As depicted, EMT-TPI achieves a MAE of 1.3 m on the z-axis and 2.53 m on the y-axis, while the x-axis error is 3.51 m, demonstrating higher uncertainty in vertical prediction

Fig. 5: Average CDF error for predicted trajectories.

compared with lateral motion.

Fig. 6: MAE along x, y, z axes compared to GT.

The 3D flight-path prediction results, as shown in Fig. 7, present two different flight path scenarios (maneuvering and complex UAV flight path trajectory). In each case, the estimated trajectory (red) closely follows the GPS+RTK ground truth (blue), demonstrating accurate trajectory prediction. Trajectory differences (between estimated and ground truth trajectories) are mainly observed during sharp turns and rapid vertical transitions. Overall, the strong overlap between the predicted and ground-truth trajectories showcases that the proposed approach can accurately reconstruct 3D UAV motion with limited drift over a long forecast horizon, even without the employment of GNSS measurements.

To assess multi-label classification performance, Precision, Recall, F1-score, and macro- and weighted-average metrics are calculated for each model (Table II). The proposed EMT-TPI achieves higher overall classification performance than MTLF-FVO, with a higher macro-average F1 score (0.79 vs. 0.67) and a higher weighted-average F1 score (0.80 vs. 0.76), indicating improved balance across classes as well as stronger support-weighted performance. These results demonstrate that EMT-TPI provides a more accurate and reliable overall state classification compared to MTLF-FVO.

VI. CONCLUSIONS

This work presents EMT-TPI, a real-time onboard multi-task framework that integrates a Transformer architecture with EKF-assisted multi-modal sensor fusion and a physics-informed training objective to jointly perform UAV state classification and trajectory prediction over a specified look-ahead horizon in GNSS-denied environments. Specifically, the EKF fuses onboard inertial telemetry with vision-based optical-flow measurements as well as weather station measurements to create an augmented measurement vector, which is then processed by a physics-informed multi-task Transformer to enforce motion consistency and therefore improve prediction robustness and performance. The proposed

Fig. 7: 3D flight path prediction results compared to the GT: (top) Maneuvering flight path, (bottom) Complex flight path.

TABLE II: Class-wise metrics for 12 s look-ahead (WS = 120 samples) of EMT-TPI vs. MTLF-FVO.

State	Precision	Recall	F1 Score
Neural Network Model: EMT-TPI			
IDLE-HOVER	0.81	0.71	0.75
ASCEND	0.87	0.91	0.89
TURN	0.85	0.68	0.76
HMSL	0.82	0.90	0.85
DESCEND	0.62	0.84	0.71
Macro-avg	0.79	0.81	0.79
Weighted-avg	0.81	0.81	0.80
Neural Network Model: MTLF-FVO			
IDLE-HOVER	0.76	0.69	0.73
ASCEND	0.74	0.88	0.80
TURN	0.74	0.52	0.61
HMSL	0.83	0.82	0.82
DESCEND	0.28	0.67	0.39
Macro-avg	0.67	0.72	0.67
Weighted-avg	0.78	0.75	0.76

EMT-TPI is trained and validated on a custom real-world dataset that consists of complex outdoor flight trajectories across different altitudes and long ranges, and provides an average trajectory prediction error of 6.875 m over a 12 s prediction horizon (without GNSS measurement information) and an F1-score of 0.79 for state classification. The overall onboard prototype is extensively evaluated in outdoor flight experiments, demonstrating performance close to the ground truth and reliable real-time operation, making it suitable for critical UAV missions.

Future work will examine the integration of additional sensing modalities to further improve performance and will expand the training dataset to strengthen both state classification and trajectory prediction capabilities.

REFERENCES

[1] H. Shakhatareh *et al.*, “Unmanned aerial vehicles (UAVs): A survey on civil applications and key research challenges,” *IEEE Access*, vol. 7,

pp. 48 572–48 634, 2019.

[2] I. Jarraya *et al.*, “GNSS-denied unmanned aerial vehicle navigation: Analyzing computational complexity, sensor fusion, and localization methodologies,” *Satellite Navigation*, vol. 6, no. 1, p. 9, 2025.

[3] D. Avola *et al.*, “UAV geo-localization for navigation: A survey,” *IEEE Access*, vol. 12, pp. 125 332–125 357, 2024.

[4] M. Corbetta *et al.*, “Real-time UAV trajectory prediction for safety monitoring in low-altitude airspace,” in *Proc. Aviation Forum*, 2019.

[5] S. Waharte and N. Trigoni, “Supporting search and rescue operations with UAVs,” in *Proc. IEEE EST*, 2010, pp. 142–147.

[6] P. Shu *et al.*, “Trajectory prediction of UAV based on LSTM,” in *Proc. ICBASE*, 2021, pp. 448–451.

[7] K. Xiao, *et al.*, “Trajectory prediction of UAV in smart city using recurrent neural networks,” in *Proc. IEEE ICC*, 2019, pp. 1–6.

[8] A. Vaswani *et al.*, “Attention is all you need,” in *Proc. NIPS*, 2017.

[9] Q. Tong *et al.*, “Long-term trajectory prediction model based on Transformer,” *IEEE Access*, vol. 11, pp. 143 695–143 703, 2023.

[10] A. Perrasquía and W. Guo, “Reservoir computing for drone trajectory intent prediction: A physics informed approach,” *IEEE Trans. Cybern.*, vol. 54, no. 9, pp. 4939–4948, 2024.

[11] N. Souli *et al.*, “An onboard UAV multi-task system for trajectory prediction and state estimation employing Transformer-and Reservoir-based networks,” *ACM Journal on Autonomous Transportation Systems*, vol. 2, no. 4, pp. 1–33, 2025.

[12] —, “A Transformer-based physics-informed network for trajectory prediction and state estimation,” in *Proc. IEEE IS2C*, 2025, pp. 1–6.

[13] C. Wang *et al.*, “A dynamics-enhanced learning model for multi-horizon trajectory prediction in autonomous vehicles,” *Information Fusion*, vol. 118, p. 102924, 2025.

[14] Y. Grigoriou *et al.*, “UAV state estimation and trajectory prediction using Transformer-based neural networks and feature-based visual odometry,” in *Proc. IEEE SMC*, 2025, pp. 206–213.

[15] H. Durrant-Whyte and T. Bailey, “Simultaneous localization and mapping: part I,” *IEEE Robot. Autom. Mag.*, vol. 13, no. 2, 2006.

[16] C. Forster *et al.*, “SVO: Fast semi-direct monocular visual odometry,” in *Proc. IEEE ICRA*, 2014, pp. 15–22.

[17] A. Loquercio *et al.*, “DroNet: Learning to fly by driving,” *IEEE Robotics & Automation Letters*, vol. 3, no. 2, pp. 1088–1095, 2018.

[18] R. W. Beard and T. W. McLain, *Small Unmanned Aircraft: Theory and Practice*. Princeton University Press, 2012.

[19] A. M. Sabatini, “Quaternion-based extended Kalman filter for determining orientation by inertial and magnetic sensing,” *IEEE Trans. Biomed. Eng.*, vol. 53, no. 7, pp. 1346–1356, 2006.

[20] S. Weiss *et al.*, “Real-time onboard visual-inertial state estimation and self-calibration of MAVs in unknown environments,” in *Proc. IEEE ICRA*, 2012, pp. 957–964.

[21] T. Qin *et al.*, “VINS-Mono: A robust and versatile monocular visual-inertial state estimator,” *IEEE Trans. Robot.*, vol. 34, no. 4, 2018.

[22] M. Bloesch *et al.*, “Robust visual inertial odometry using a direct EKF-based approach,” in *Proc. IEEE/RSJ IROS*, 2015, pp. 298–304.

[23] K. Zhang *et al.*, “Trajectory prediction for autonomous driving using spatial-temporal graph attention Transformer,” *IEEE Trans. Intell. Transp. Syst.*, vol. 23, no. 11, pp. 22 343–22 353, 2022.

[24] J. Ren *et al.*, “Long-term trajectory prediction of hypersonic glide vehicle based on physics-informed Transformer,” *IEEE Trans. Aerosp. Electron. Syst.*, vol. 59, no. 6, pp. 9551–9561, 2023.

[25] M. Geng *et al.*, “A physics-informed Transformer model for vehicle trajectory prediction on highways,” *Transp. Res. Part C Emerg. Technol.*, vol. 154, p. 104272, 2023.

[26] R. Caruana, “Multitask learning,” *Machine Learning*, vol. 28, 1997.

[27] S. Ruder, “An overview of multi-task learning in deep neural networks,” *arXiv:1706.05098 [cs.LG]*, 2017.

[28] A. Palamas *et al.*, “A multi-task learning framework for drone state identification and trajectory prediction,” in *Proc. IEEE DCROSS-IoT*, 2023, pp. 676–683.

[29] R. Hartley and A. Zisserman, *Multiple View Geometry in Computer Vision*. Cambridge University Press, 2003.

[30] R. Szeliski, *Computer Vision: Algorithms and Applications*. Springer, 2022.

[31] P.-T. De Boer *et al.*, “A tutorial on the cross-entropy method,” *Annals of operations research*, vol. 134, no. 1, pp. 19–67, 2005.

[32] F. Xu, “Faster scalable ML model deployment using ONNX and open source tools,” in *Proc. IEEE Infrastructure Conference*, 2020.

[33] F. P. Moreno *et al.*, “Prediction of air traffic complexity through a dynamic complexity indicator and machine learning models,” *J. Air Transp. Manag.*, vol. 119, p. 102632, 2024.

[34] Y. Grigoriou *et al.*, “Drone onboard multi-modal sensor and feature-based visual odometry dataset for complex outdoor scenarios,” Mar. 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15089283>